

Adsorption of Pb^{2+} ions from water media using the novel CaO-CdO/ZSM-5 zeolite nanocomposite adsorbent

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Abstract

ZSM-5 is a porous zeolite material that reveals good activity for the adsorption of heavy metals and other contaminants for effluent purification. In this scientific research, we synthesized the novel CaO-CdO/ZSM-5 zeolite nanocomposite adsorbent and studied the effects of different parameters on the adsorption of Pb^{2+} ions from water media for the first time. About 99.2% adsorption removal efficiency was obtained after contact time of 60 min and adsorbent amount of 0.1 g/L for initial Pb^{2+} concentration of 200 mg/L at pH 8 and temperature of 60 °C. The adsorption kinetic fit well via the pseudo-second order model. Furthermore, the adsorption results were reproduced using the Langmuir isotherm with a maximum adsorption capacity of mg/g. The thermodynamic data displayed that the adsorption of Pb^{2+} ions over the CaO-CdO/ZSM-5 nanocomposite were endothermic and spontaneous.

Keywords: CaO-CdO/ZSM-5, zeolite, nanocomposite, Pb^{2+} ions, adsorption.